

A PROPOSAL OF METHODOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT

This study addresses main questions when developing a soil monitoring programme and underlines possible ways to harmonize national programmes with EU Soil Observatory

REVIEW OF MONITORING PROGRAMMES

Stocktake the description of monitoring networks across EJP SOIL partners through the use of a questionnaire.

COMMON SOIL HEALTH INDICATORS

Five common parameters: Soil pH, texture, organic carbon, calcium/carbonate content and nutrients. There are harmonization demands in sampling design, area, depths, pre-analysis handling and analytical methods.

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A REVIEW OF EXISTING SOIL MONITORING SYSTEMS TO PAVE THE WAY FOR THE EU SOIL OBSERVATORY

Towards harmonized European soil information system

Identify common approaches to harmonize and compare national monitoring initiatives and EU Soil Observatory.

Develop interpretation values/scoring approaches.

EJP SOIL INNOVATION HIGHLIGHTS

EJP SOIL WP6

Monitoring
Mapping
Indicators &
Benchmark values
Data management

EU Soil Observatory

Monitoring
EU Dashboard
Data Center
R&I
Open forum

*Monitoring
Indicators
Data*

TOWARDS CLIMATE-SMART SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF AGRICULTURAL SOILS

EJP SOIL is a European Joint Programme on Agricultural Soil Management addressing key societal challenges including climate change and future food supply. <https://ejpsoil.eu/>

The goal is to improve the understanding of agricultural soil management by finding synergies in research, strengthening research communities and raising public awareness.

1100+ experts, 24 countries, addressing multiple aspects of soil management across different European agroecosystems.

EJP SOIL WORK PACKAGE WP6 SOIL INFORMATION & REPORTING

The objective of the work package is the development of an agreed knowledge base (monitoring, mapping, indicators and benchmark values) and database to improve the European contribution towards international reporting on soils, and the accuracy of European agricultural policies.

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TARGET EJP SOIL EXPECTED IMPACT AND EU MISSION SOIL OBJECTIVES

Supporting harmonised European soil information and fostering the uptake of climate-smart sustainable soil management practices.

SOIL MISSION: reduce desertification, conserve soil organic carbon stocks, prevent erosion and improve soil structure and biodiversity

HIGHLIGHT FACTS FROM:

EJP SOIL WORK PACKAGE 6
Deliverable 6.3

Applicability:
all climatic zones according to
Metzger et al. (2005)
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